
A Review on Anaemia In Pregnancy: Prevalence, Challenges In Iron Supplementation Adherence and Strategies For Improved Maternal Health Outcomes

Patel Punyak Kamleshbhai*, Dr. Hetal D. Solanki, Patel Alka Umeshbhai, Ganvit Tara Arjunbhai, Sonkar Rahul Ravi and Gavli Kaushika Amratbhai

Department of Master of Pharmacy in Pharmacy Practice,
Students of “Shivam Pharmaceutical Studies and Research Centre”, Anand, Gujarat
*patelpunyak22@gmail.com

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted on: 25-03-2025

Published on: 15-04-2025

Keywords:

Anaemia, Nutritional and Iron Deficiency, Maternal Health, Supplementation, Risk Factors

ABSTRACT

Anaemia during pregnancy is a global health concern, primarily caused by iron and folate deficiencies. Increased iron and folate requirements during pregnancy make supplementation essential to prevent adverse maternal and fetal outcomes. Poor adherence is still a major problem even though iron and folic acid supplements are widely available in pregnant woman care programs. Factors contributing to non-adherence include side effects, lack of awareness, socio-economic barriers, and inadequate healthcare support. This study evaluates the prevalence, causes, and consequences of anaemia during pregnancy and explores strategies to improve adherence to iron supplementation. Findings indicate that while adherence rates are relatively high, non-adherence persists due to multiple factors. Addressing these barriers through targeted educational interventions, better healthcare access, and personalized support systems is crucial in reducing anaemia-related complications. Enhancing adherence to iron therapy not only improves maternal health outcomes but also ensures better neonatal health and long-term well-being.

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15222778>

INTRODUCTION: Pregnancy-related anaemia is a worldwide concern. The two main causes of nutritional anaemia have been reported to be iron and folate deficiencies. Because iron and folate needs increased during pregnancy, there is a greater chance of developing iron and folate deficiencies if supplements are skipped during this time. One of the WHO's worldwide reduction goals is to reduce the incidence of anaemia in women of reproductive age by 50% by 2025, with current data shows that it has not changed much over the last twenty years.^[1] The WHO advises all pregnant women take 400 µg of folic acid and 60 mg of iron daily during the first six-month period of their pregnancy. Higher rates of maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity, as well as the effects of postpartum infections and maternal blood loss, are linked to pregnancy-related anaemia. The most frequent cause of anaemia is frequently iron deficiency. Iron deficiency anaemia may give rise to low birth weight, reduced immunity to illness, poor cognitive development, and reduced job capacity.^[2]

A cofactor of various the hemoproteins and non-hemoproteins, iron is an important nutrient. It is a part of the homeoprotein's myoglobin and hemoglobin in red blood cells, which carry and store oxygen in muscles and other tissues, respectively.^[1] The most impacted populations are often children aged 6 to 24 months, pregnant women, and postpartum mothers. It is very common in less developed nations, where bacterial and parasite diseases can deplete iron stores in addition to inadequate nutrition. Iron supplements are given to expectant mothers by many antenatal care programs, although their efficacy in lowering maternal Anaemia has been insufficient.^[1]

Anaemia is known as a decrease in haemoglobin and red blood cell counts. It is a sign of an underlying condition and can be classified as macrocytic or microcytic. Patients with anaemia typically show mild signs like weakness, lethargy, and tiredness. Severe anaemia shows as syncope, shortness of breath, and a reduced tolerance to activity. The assessment and management of Anaemia are described in this activity, along with the function of the team of specialists in the care of patients with this illness.^[3]

The most likely cause of these programs' failure is poor adherence to iron treatment (for example, missing pills). The degree to which individuals take their drugs as directed by their healthcare professionals is sometimes referred to as adherence to a pharmaceutical regimen. Individual patient adherence rates are typically expressed as the proportion of the medication's recommended dosages that the patient actually takes during a given time frame. In addition to patient behavior, variables beyond the patient's control can also contribute to poor compliance.^[3]

Some of the reasons why people may not adhere to iron deficiency treatment include inadequate program support, insufficient service, and patient concerns such as nausea, migration, side effects, and unhappiness with the amount and frequency of pills taken.^[2] Anaemia is a decrease in the amount of red blood cells. Anaemia is not a diagnosis; rather, it is a symptom of an underlying disease. A patient's prognosis is influenced by the severity of onset, the cause of anaemia, and the existence of other comorbidities, particularly cardiovascular illness. The majority of people have symptoms related to anaemia when their haemoglobin level drops below 7.0 g/dL.^[3]

Poor adherence to iron supplements has been related to the side symptoms (constipation, nausea) that women can get during iron therapy. Actually, the most frequent reason given by women for not taking iron supplements was their unavailability. Accurate and acceptable techniques for identifying Anaemia, evaluating its severity, and tracking therapy response are essential for the successful management of Anaemia during pregnancy. Timely treatment of mild-to-moderate Anaemia in women is likely to lower the risk of blood transfusions and the need for them by preventing the development of more severe Anaemia. There are extra instant benefits for both mother and child when severe Anaemia is prevented.^[2]

The kidney releases erythropoietin, which is the main factor that stimulates the formation of red blood cells. erythropoietin levels are typically inversely proportional to hemoglobin concentration, and tissue hypoxia is the primary activator of erythropoietin generation. In other words, someone with anaemia and low haemoglobin has a higher amount of erythropoietin. erythropoietin levels, however, are lower than expected in anaemic patients with renal failure. In Anaemia of Chronic Disease, erythropoietin levels are usually greater but not as high as they should be, indicating a relative erythropoietin insufficiency.

Laboratory cut-offs for normal haemoglobin (Hgb) will vary slightly, ranges are as follows:

- In males 13.5 to 18.0 g/dL
- In females 12.0 to 15.0 g/dL
- In children 11.0 to 16.0 g/dL
- Varied by trimester across pregnancy, sometimes above 10.0 g/dL^[3]

A child's most vulnerable period is in the neonatal period. Worldwide, a significant proportion of infants are born underweight each year. The majority of these deaths are caused by maternal and infant malnutrition.^[14]

Originally approved for use in assessing adherence in patients receiving antiretroviral treatment, Simplified Medication Adherence Questionnaire is a short and simple tool that offers the patient directly about her medication-taking behaviours. Pregnant women's adherence to nutritional deficiency treatment has been measured using this field method. The validity of a modified SMAQ questionnaire for use on pregnant women is presented in this study.^[15]

1.1. Anaemia:

Anaemia occurs when balance between destruction and production of red blood cells disturbed by blood loss, impaired red cell formation due to iron, B12, folic acid and increased destruction of RBCs in blood.^[4]

Several red cell defects, such as those resulting from production, maturation, and synthesis of haemoglobin defects like iron deficiency anaemia, mutations in haemoglobin maturation like thalassemia, abnormal haemoglobin synthesis like haemoglobin disorders, sickle cell anaemia, and thalassemia, and physical loss of red blood cells like haemolytic anaemias, can cause anaemia.^[5]

In this situation, the body fails to produce enough red blood cells to fulfil its oxygen requirements. Understanding the different classes can help both identify the symptoms and prevent anaemia in the first place.^[5]

Figure 1. Body iron distribution and storage [5]

Figure 2. Intestinal absorption, transport, utilization and storage of iron [4]

Type of Anaemia	Hemoglobin Count (gm/dL) min	Hemoglobin Count (gm/dL) max
Mild- Anaemia	8	12
Moderate- Anaemia	5	8
Severe-Anaemia	5	Less than 5

Table 1. Classification of Anaemia ^[5]

The size of the red blood cell and the quantity of haemoglobin in each cell are also used to categorize anaemia.[6]

- a) Microcytic anaemia with smaller cells.
- b) Macrocytic anaemia with larger cells

1.2 Types of Anaemia:

^[6]

1. iron-deficiency Anaemia
2. Pernicious Anaemia
3. Hemolytic Anaemia
4. Sickle cell Anaemia
5. Thalassemia
6. Aplastic Anaemia
7. Megaloblastic Anaemia ^[10]

1. Iron-deficiency Anaemia:

One of the more prevalent anaemia worldwide, including in India, is the IDA. This illness is characterized by an iron shortage in the blood.

The protein haemoglobin, which is present in red blood cells, transports oxygen throughout the body. Iron is required by the body to produce hemoglobin.

A low iron intake results in reduced production of red blood cells and hemoglobin, which causes Anaemia. The human body needs iron for several different processes, chief among them being the production of hemoglobin. ^[6]

When dietary iron intake is low to meet iron requirements over time, particularly throughout times of life when iron requirements are very high, ID develops.

Iron-deficient erythropoiesis, storage iron depletion, and IDA are the three stages that ID usually progresses through. According to the WHO, serum ferritin should be used for measure iron status.

The acute phase response raises serum ferritin, a sensitive indicator of ID and a measure of body storage iron; elevated sTfR levels signify tissue ID.

Since inflammation affects several markers of iron status, acute phase proteins including alpha-1-acid glycoprotein and C-reactive protein should be assessed whenever possible.

Since the late 1990s, it has been estimated that 2 billion people worldwide live with ID, it is believed to be contributing to around 50% of all incidents of anaemia.

A recent comprehensive analysis of anaemia data that provided factor-specific attribution for 17 anaemia related diseases found that iron deficiency was the most common trigger in almost every region analysed.

The WHO estimated the "proportion of all Anaemia amenable to iron" to be 42% of Anaemia in children and 50% of Anaemia in pregnant and nonpregnant women based on changes in Hb concentration from iron supplementation studies.

ID was significantly less important in nations with high levels of inflammation and Anaemia prevalence above 40%. The percentage of anaemia people with ID changes depending on contextual factors, therefore low iron consumption cannot always be considered to be the primary cause, even though ID is still a primary cause in many situations.

However, the majority of Anaemia control efforts revolve upon iron interventions (such as fortification, dietary changes, and supplementation), and the WHO now has 17 guidelines on supplements containing iron.^[7]

Red cell mass increases during pregnancy, but plasma volume increases approximately as well, causing physiological dilutional anaemia.

It is suggested that that in order fulfil additional needs of fetal red cell synthesis, the stomach improves its capacity to absorb iron during pregnancy. Menstruation is stopped in part to meet the increasing requirement. However, anaemia could happen if there is inadequate intake of iron.^[10]

Both iron excess and iron shortage can be dangerous. damage of liver, failure of heart, diabetes mellitus, gap joint discomfort, and skin colour changes are just a few of the issues that iron overload can bring. Patients with hereditary hemochromatosis, a rare genetic condition marked by iron build-up in several body organs, experience them.^[20]

Figure 3. Iron deficiency Anaemia ^[3]

Pathophysiology:

Premenopausal women have reduced iron storage because of frequent menstrual blood loss, whereas adult males have 35 to 45 mg of iron per kilogram of body weight in a physiologically normal condition. More than two-thirds of the body's iron is found in haemoglobin, which is found in reticuloendothelial macrophages, bone marrow, and circulating erythroblasts and erythrocytes. The rest of the iron is found in myoglobin and enzymes, with ferritin, which is mostly stored in the liver. Just 0.1 percent of total body iron is connected to transferrin in plasma.

This sort of iron can go into various tissues after binding to the transferrin receptor. Since iron is a highly reactive metal, it can rapidly transform into plasma iron by causing the generation of harmful free radicals. The duodenum absorbs a tiny amount of iron (1–2 mg daily) from the food, but the majority of plasma iron comes from iron scavenged from senescent erythrocytes by macrophages.

Through monthly blood, sweat, skin peeling, and urine excretion, up to two milligrams of iron are lost each day. The failure of a regulating system for iron excretion means that iron intake, intestinal absorption, and iron cycling must all be balanced. ^[18]

Causes and Risk factors of iron deficiency: ^[8]

- Low iron in diet
- Iron absorb inability
- Gastrointestinal abnormalities
- Internal bleeding
- Menopause
- Excessive donating blood
- Exercise
- Medications – anticoagulants, NSAIDS
- Hemodialysis
- Blood donation
- Urinary tract- Malignancy
- Trauma
- Gynecological & Obstetric- pregnancy and lactation
- Helicobacter pylori
- Obesity
- Inflammatory bowel disease
- Genetic disorder

Symptoms: Fatigue, irritability, light-headedness, palpitations, headache, enlarged or sore tongue, changed taste, and pregnancy A problem risk is elevated by anaemia.

Treatments:

To treat the anaemia and restore storage, all patients should take iron supplements. For the majority of patients, oral ferrous form of iron is affordable, secure, and efficient. To treat the anaemia and restore stores of body iron, depending on the state of the stores, the drug may need to be taken regularly for up to six months.

200 milligrams of ferrous sulphate twice or thrice daily is the usual course of treatment. For the hemoglobin level to rise by 1 g/dL, one to two weeks are needed.

Two to three days after beginning successful therapy, the medication's effects should begin to increase. Some individuals experience nausea or gastrointestinal pain, which is typically linked to the amount of elemental iron they take. Iron is better tolerated when given with meals, although the quantity absorbed is often decreased.

Because they contain less elemental iron, additional iron salts have been wanted; they frequently cause less adverse consequences.

Oral dosages of iron are better absorbed by the body in the early stages of treatment. For the first two to three weeks, absorption is typically 15% of intake; above that, it averages 5%.^[8]

Ferrous fumarate, ferrous gluconate, and ferrous sulphate are the three most often used oral ferrous iron treatments. In an effort to enhance their pregnancy experience, the WHO recommends pregnant and postpartum women with IDA to raise their regular elemental amount of iron consumption from the recommended daily prenatal dose of 30 to 60 milligrams to 120 milligrams until their haemoglobin levels recover to normal.^[22]

Prevention:

There exists "an extremely high level of hidden hunger, with stunting, iron deficiency anaemia, and vitamin A deficiency all being highly prevalent" in certain sub-Saharan African, Indian, and Afghan nations. These figures are projected to rise in the wake of the economic downturn and climate change, and disparities in early childhood development will be caused by additional poverty-related issues. Long-term detrimental effects on motor functioning and cerebral development will result from the effects during pregnancy and the first year of life. To address this hidden burden of disease, several micronutrient therapies (such as those involving iron, zinc, and vitamin A) are actually required.

Deworming, preventative iron therapy, and fortified supplemental diets are recommended to address iron deficiency. In South Africa, mandated food fortification for wheat flour and maize was implemented in 2003. ^[19]

Preparation	Content of Iron(mg)
Tab Ferrous gluconate 300mg	35
Tab Ferrous sulphate 210mg	68
Syp ferrous fumarate 140mg in 5ml	45
Tab Ferrous fumarate 322mg	100
Syp ferrous sulphate 125mg in 1ml	25
Syp sodium federate 190mg in 5ml	27.5

Figure 4. Elemental iron content of common oral preparations ^[10]

2. Pernicious Anaemia (Pernicious means destructive or injurious):

This type of Anaemia was formerly referred to as "dangerous" since it was believed to be a fatal disease. Treatment options currently include B-12 oral pills or injections. ^[3]

The body needs it to produce new cells, including numerous RBCs that were produced daily. In meat, fishes, eggs, and milk has found large amount of vitamin B12.

Deficiency of vitamin B12 and, sometimes different of factors might cause Anaemia. B12 deficiency, or low vitamin B12 intake, can cause Anaemia.

Pernicious Anaemia typically occurs after the age of fifty. Generally speaking, it comes in families, with men being less likely than women to be affected. It's more common in those with other autoimmune illnesses. Numerous drugs may potentially have an impact on vitamin B12 absorption. The most common ones are neomycin, metformin, anticonvulsants used to treat epilepsy, and colchicine. ^[9]

Causes:

- Inadequate diet

- Vitamin B12 deficiency
- Infection of gastrointestinal system

Sign and Symptoms:

- Tiredness
- Inability of breath
- Ligh colored skin
- Pain in chest
- Balance inadequate
- Reflexes that are slow

3. Hemolytic Anaemia:

Haemolytic anaemia is characterized by damaged red blood cells (RBCs) that stay separated from the circulation until the end of their normal lifespan. Individuals of all ages, backgrounds, and genders are at risk of this kind of anaemia.

Examples of hereditary anaemia types Anaemia include hereditary spherocytosis, sickle cell Anaemia, and thalassemia. Hemolytic Anaemia has been eradicated because some illnesses and substances can harm red blood cells (RBCs). The most severe kind of hemolytic Anaemia is brought on by receiving red blood cells transfused from the incorrect blood type.

Symptoms:

- Jaundice
- Exhaustion
- Difficulties in breath,
- headaches sign of low red blood cells count
- Yellow skin,
- pain in chest.
- Pain in abdomen

4. Sickle cell Anaemia:

Anaemia of sickle cell has, RBCs function like blades. Because of its aberrant hemoglobin, it has a scissors-like form and is more difficult to flow through blood arteries. It seems that outbreaks in children and during pregnancy are worsened.

Pain from blocked blood arteries might result in severe infections and organ damage. Blood loss results from sick cells' 10- to 20-day half-lives, and the body's inability to replace dying RBCs with new ones.

Symptoms:

- Pale skin
- Breathlessness
- Dizziness
- Gets tired quickly

5. Thalassemia:

Thalassemia was a blood disorder in which the body generates abnormal red blood cells and little haemoglobin. Beta and alpha are the two most common types of thalassemia.

Alpha large thalassemia, additionally referred to as a hydrops fatal, is a severe variant of beta thalassemia, while major beta thalassemia, also known as Ooley Anaemia, is a severe version of the condition. Men and women are equally affected by thalassemia, which is more prevalent in Italy, Greece, the Middle East, Asia, and Africa.

Red blood cell haemoglobin consists of two different kinds of protein chains: alpha and beta globin. Red blood cells aren't able to store enough oxygen if your body fails to generate enough of these protein chains.

Genes regulate the formation of hemoglobin chains. Thalassemia arises from the absence or alteration of these genes. A genetic condition called thalassemia is inherited and handed down through the generations.

Symptoms:

- Dark urine

- Jaundice
- Symptoms of liver disease
- Appetite problems
- Bone problems
- Pale skin tone

6. Aplastic Anaemia:

Bleeding, infections, arrhythmias, enlarged hearts, and heart failure may arise from blood diseases such as aplastic anaemia, in which the bone marrow is unable to generate enough red blood cells. Numerous health issues, including arrhythmias, enlarged hearts, heart failure, infections, and bleeding, might result from this. Aplastic anaemia is brought on by damage to the stem cells in the bone marrow.

Numerous acquired conditions, including poisons like benzene, arsenic, and pesticides, can cause aplastic Anaemia. radiation and chemotherapy, HIV and hepatitis are examples of infectious diseases; autoimmune diseases include rheumatoid arthritis and are treated with drugs like chloramphenicol. conditions that are inherited such as Fanconi Anaemia, Schwachman Diamond syndrome, hair loss, and Diamond Blackfan Anaemia can lead to aplastic Anaemia.

The most typical aplastic Anaemia symptoms include headaches, tiredness, confusion, chest discomfort, pale appearance, teeth, and nail beds, and exhausted hands and feet. Aplastic Anaemia is treated with medications, bone marrow stem cell transplants, and blood transfusions. ^[9] .

Symptoms:

- Fatigue
- Yellowish skin
- Difficulty in breath
- Head pain
- Pain in chest

Fig.5. Aplastic Anaemia bone marrow Contributed

Treatment:

- blood transfusion
- Transplant of bone marrow stem cell

7. Megaloblastic Anaemia:^[10]

- The macrocytic anaemias are the megaloblastic anaemias. The maturation of cells that produce blood in the bone marrow is abnormal.
- White blood cells and platelets may also be affected, in addition to abnormal red blood cells. Lacks in folate and vitamin B12 are the two major causes.
- A specific autoimmune condition called pernicious anaemia results in vitamin B12 malabsorption due to an absence of intrinsic factor.

Folate deficiency:

- The dietary intake of folate is limited for the majority of the global population.
- Since body reserves are small, weaknesses quickly arise when food intake decreased or demand for folate rises.

- A typical diet contains enough of folate. Folate is found in comparatively high concentrations in fruit, green vegetables, and yeast. Dietary deficiencies are typical, despite the relative a lot of folate in many meals, either as the only reason for folic acid deficiency anaemia or when used combination with improved folate use.

Pathophysiology:

Vitamin B12 deficiency:

- While true anaemia is less usual, strict vegans (such as Hindus) often experience low vitamin B12 levels as a consequence of their diet. Vitamin B12 deficiency anaemia will develop in

every person who undergo a whole gastrectomy and in as many as 15% of patients who have had a partial gastrectomy.

- It may be found in seafood, eggs, meat, egg-based dairy products, and milk. Cooking usually does not degrade vitamin B12. The range of daily needs is 1–3 µcg.
- Inadequate intake or malabsorption results in deficiency. Vitamin B12, also known as cyanocobalamin, can only be obtained through diets that contain animal products.
- Deficiency results from either long-term insufficient intake or, more frequently in the West, from poor absorption brought on by a lack of intrinsic factor.
- Although the jejunum does experience passive absorption, this process is extremely ineffective and often makes up less than 1% of an oral dosage.

Epidemiology: ^[3] ^[18] ^[24]

Up to one-third of people worldwide suffer from Anaemia, a very prevalent illness. It often has no symptoms, is moderate, and not need to treatment. Pregnant women, elderly people, and women of reproductive years have greater rates, which rise with age.

Additionally, about 20% of people over 85 have this condition. Anaemia affects 50–60% of those living in nursing homes. Iron, folate, and vitamin B12 deficiencies are among the nutritional deficiencies that cause Anaemia in about one-third of senior individuals.

Evidence of chronic inflammation or renal failure is found in another one-third of individuals. In the past, slight iron deficiency Women of reproductive years regularly suffer from anaemia, which is frequently caused on by insufficient dietary iron intake and monthly iron loss during periods.

Elderly individuals also often suffer from anaemia, which can be brought on by insufficient diet, particularly in terms of iron and folic acid. Alcoholics, the homeless, and those that were ignored or mistreated constitute the other populations who are at risk.

Newly diagnosed anaemia requires more research until proven in various ways, especially for those over 55. This is especially true for men of any age who have anaemia. The development of anaemia is significantly affected by race in addition to gender and age, with an increased frequency among African Americans.^[3]

The World health organization estimates that iron supplementation could completely eliminate 42% of anaemia cases in children and 50% of anaemia cases in women. In the US deficiency of iron affects eleven percent of children aged six months to five years, fifteen percent of premenopausal women, and eighteen percent pregnant women, the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, to be precise. The disadvantaged subpopulations who are more likely to experience iron deficiency and anaemia include poor persons, members of tribal groups, refugees, and migrants from countries with low or middle incomes.^[18]

Further, it is the main nutritional shortage observed in the developed countries; up to 50% of cases arise from inadequate iron intake. Pregnancy is linked to higher iron requirements, thereby increasing the risk of iron deficiency anaemia. Decreased iron reserves in a new born increase the chance of later developing iron deficiency anaemia. Iron shortage may result from multiple factors, such as insufficient consumption, malabsorption, bleeding, and higher physiological requirements. Poor nutritional intake is typically noted in cases of malnutrition, vegan diets, chronic illnesses, and low socio-economic conditions.^[23]

Research shows that the most frequent cause of nutritional anaemia everywhere is iron deficiency, which is serious health related public concern, particularly in poorer nations. Haemoglobin levels below 11 g/dl indicate mild anaemia during pregnancy, between 7 and 9.9 g/dl are considered moderate anaemia, and less than 7 g/dl is termed severe anaemia, which is typically brought on by an iron shortage.

Over 40% of pregnant women worldwide were anaemic, according to the WHO 2012 data. Iron deficiency causes almost half of this burden. Pregnancy-related anaemia has serious negative effects on the mother and the developing foetus. At present, the primary risk factors for anaemia during pregnancy are micronutrient deficiencies of iron and folic acid, which also raise maternal mortality and result in poor neonatal health.^[24]

1.3 Pathophysiology:^[3]

The pathophysiology of anaemia is greatly influenced by its underlying its cause. For example, the restoration of blood volume with internal and extracellular fluid reduces the remaining red blood cells (RBCs) during severe haemorrhagic anaemia.

Red blood cells develop in the bone marrow and then released into the circulatory system. Around one percent of RBCs are eliminated from circulation each day. RBCs are removed or destroyed as a result of an imbalance in production, that leads to anaemia.

Mechanisms involved in Anaemia mentioned here:

1. Increased RBC destruction

➤ Loss of blood

- Menorrhagia, trauma, surgery, and acute bleeding
- Heavy menstrual bleeding, chronic blood loss in the gastrointestinal tract (due to the hookworm infestation, wounds, etc.), and the stool losses (BPH, renal cancer, schistosomiasis) are instances of chronic conditions.

➤ Hemolytic anaemia

- associated with hypersplenism, acquired immune-mediated, infection-related, microangiopathic, and blood transfusion-related
- Hereditary enzymatic diseases, sickle cell haemoglobin disorders, abnormalities in red blood cell metabolism, and abnormalities in the formation of red blood cell membranes

2. Defective erythropoiesis

- Microcytic
- Normocytic,
- Macrocytic Medications – anticoagulants, NSAIDS
- Hemodialysis
- Blood donation

1.4 Medication Adherence:

- In the defined as “the extent to which patient’s behavior corresponds with agreed recommendations from a healthcare provider”.^[12]
- Medication adherence is one of the most crucial factors that determines therapeutics consequences, particularly in those with chronic illnesses like Anaemia, hypertension.
- Regardless of the medication's efficiency, it cannot be effective unless the patient takes it.

- Since it significantly affects the advantages of modern medical care and puts a heavy cost on both individual patients and the health care system overall, low drug adherence has gained importance. ^[11]

Non – adherence types: ^[11]

- Patients have shown non-adherence to their treatment in a variety of conditions. They have been divided into groups according to whether the prescription was filled, if the prescription drug was used excessively or insufficiently, or whether non-prescription medications were used.
- There are two categories of medication non-adherence.

A. Primary

Non-Intentional

- The patient does not have a prescription filled. This might be the result of financial difficulties or medicine shortages.

B. Secondary

Intentional

- The patient refuses to follow the medication on his own initiative.
- The patient may take less medication than recommended because they believe it is too high, or they may take more medication in hopes of recovering from their illness more quickly.

1.5 Factors affecting Adherence: ^{[12][17][21]}

The World Health Organization (WHO) states that one of the major problems in the medical care of patients with chronic illnesses is medication non-adherence. A number of factors combine to determine the multifaceted events of adherence.

Sr. No.	Factors	Description
1.	Social /Economical	A. Patients with family social support showed better adherence. B. Unstable living due to a lack of social support or family situations such as homelessness and restricted access to medical facilities. C. Lack of Financial resource, medication cost D. . Burdensome Schedule
2.	Provider -Patient /system of health care	A. Relationship of patient and provider B. Ineffective communication on the advantages of taking medicine C. Medication side effects and use instructions could lead to nonadherence.
3.	Conditional factors related	A. Patients with chronic illnesses (like high blood pressure or osteoporosis) who necessitate long-term medication delivery show a considerable drop in adherence to treatment regimens with time. B. The patient should be aware of the condition and what will happen if therapy is not provided.
4.	Related to therapy factor	A. Medication regimen complexity (daily number of doses) B. Therapy duration C. Lack of therapy's immediate benefits D. Treatment causes lifestyle interruptions or requires major behavioural changes.

5.	Related factor to patient	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Impairment in visualize 2. Impairment in Healing 3. Impairment in cognitive 4. In elderly people, swallowing issues may raise the risk of nonadherence.
----	---------------------------	---

Table 2. Factors Affecting Adherence

There are a number of variables that may impact medication adherence in the general population, but pregnant women may be more susceptible to certain influences. Given the risk of damage that untreated maternal illness could do to the foetus, pregnant women may be encouraged to take their medications for the baby's health. However, there is evidence that women may refuse to take their medicine because they are worried about the possible negative consequences on the foetus.^[21]

Methods of Measuring Adherences: ^[13].

Methods for Measuring Medication adherence can be categorized into two basic types.

A. Direct Methods

1. Therapy of Direct observation
2. Determination of the level of the drug
3. Measurement of biological marker

1. *Direct observation Treatment:*

- It is most precise technique.
- The patient could hide the prescribed drug in their oral cavity and then throw it away.

2. *Measurement Level of drug:*

- Drug concentration is measured using biological tests.
- These measures are intrusive often costly.
- Drug or food interactions, physiological variations, dosage schedules, and the drug's half-life can all have an effect.

3. Biological Marker determination:

- Not all drugs can be used with this strategy.
- As an instance, riboflavin is a biological marker that can only be non-qualitative to detect.
- The accuracy of the test might also be hampered by medication and dietary interactions.

B. In-Direct Methods

1. Self-report of the patient
2. Counting pills
3. Clinical response
4. Data refilling
5. Monitoring of drug electronically

1. Self-report of patient:

☐ Self-reported measures, such questionnaires and diaries, are very easy to administer. However, there may occasionally be reluctance to regularly write their drug administration details in a journal or to answer a series of questions.

☐ Variability in their surveys, memory times, and treatment response are all components of self-medication adherence.

☐ Self-reports provide a very specific assessment of drug adherence behaviour.^[12]

2. Counting pills:

☐ Some of the easiest ways to assess adherence to oral medicines is to count pills.

☐ It does, however, require that patients bring a full supply of medications to each appointment with the doctor and refrain from destroying the correct pill count by throwing away unnecessary medication while taking it as recommended.^[13]

3. Clinical response:

□ Clinical response measurement is carried out at regular visits with medical professionals and may already be part of the standard of care monitoring for the condition being treated.

4. Data refilling:

□ These techniques also make it possible to evaluate a lot of patients over a long period of time.

5. Monitoring of drug electronically:

□ Specialized microchips embedded in medicine bottles serve as electronic drug monitors, such as the medication event monitoring system (MEMS), which keeps track of each bottle opening.

□ so long as each bottle opening really represents a single administration and the patient refrains from transferring medication into another container, the MEMS provides an accurate record of the patient's medication-taking behaviour.

□ In addition to being costly, these systems typically need the frequent transfer of data from the microchips to the appropriate software application.

CONCLUSION:

Anaemia during pregnancy remains a significant global health challenge, primarily driven by iron and folate deficiencies. Maternal and fetal difficulties are on the rise as a result of poor adherence to prenatal supplements programs, which are still present. The main elements influencing adherence are highlighted in this study, such as adverse effects, a lack of knowledge financial limitations, and access to healthcare. To increase iron supplementation compliance, these issues must be addressed through better patient support networks, education, and medical interventions. Enhancing adherence techniques will not only lower the prevalence of anemia but also enhance maternal health, lessen perinatal hazards, and advance the general welfare of both mother and child. To successfully reduce pregnancy-related anemia, ongoing initiatives in community awareness, healthcare professional participation, and policy implementation are crucial.

REFERENCE:

- 1 Givens, D. I., Anitha, S., & Giromini, C. (2024). Anaemia in India and its prevalence and

- multifactorial aetiology: a narrative review. *Nutrients*, 16(11), 1673.
- 2 KHATTAB, M. S. (2014). Assessment of Adherence to Iron and Folic Acid Supplementation and Prevalence of Anemia in Pregnant Women.
 - 3 Turner J, Parsi M, Badireddy M, anaemia in statpearl, Statpearls Publishing, www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK499994.
 - 4 Tripathi, K. D. (2018). *Essentials of medical pharmacology*. Jaypee Brothers medical publishers.
 - 5 Soundarya N, Suganthi P, A review of Anaemia -types, Causes, symptoms and treatments, *Journal of science and technology investigation* -ISSN: 2456-8082.
 - 6 Johny, J. (2021). *A review article on anaemia*. *Biosci Biotechnol Res Commun* 14: 28–32.
 - 7 Chaparro, C. M., & Suchdev, P. S. (2019). Anemia epidemiology, pathophysiology, and etiology in low-and middle-income countries. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1450(1), 15-31.
 - 8 Rusch JA, van der Westhuizen DJ, Gill RS, Louw VJ. Diagnosing iron deficiency: Controversies and novel metrics. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Anaesthesiology*. 2023 Dec 1;37(4):451-67.
 - 9 Hussien, R. S., Jabuk, S. I., Altaee, Z. M., & Al-Maamori, A. M. (2023). Review of anemia: types and causes. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 4(7), 3.
 - 10 Walker, Roger, and Clive Edwards. "Clinical pharmacy and therapeutics, Churchill Livingstone." London, (2004): 321-322.
 - 11 G Parthsarthy, Karin Nyfort Hansen, Milap C Nahata, a textbook of clinical pharmacy practice 2nd edition.
 - 12 Lam, W. Y., & Fresco, P. (2015). Medication adherence measures: an overview. *BioMed research international*, 2015(1), 217047.
 - 13 Kreys, E. (2016). Measurements of medication adherence: in search of a gold standard. *Journal of Clinical Pathways*, 2(8), 43-47.
 - 14 Shrestha, S. Shakya, et al. "Adherence to iron, folic acid and calcium supplement and factors affecting it among the Antenatal care attending women in a tertiary care hospital: A cross sectional study." *Kathmandu University Medical Journal* 18.2 (2020): 83-90.
 - 15 estudio VATREN, G., Ortega Suárez, F. J., Ortega Suárez, F. J., Sánchez Plumed, J., Sánchez Plumed, J., Valentín, P., ... & Grupo de Estudio VATREN. (2011). Validation on

- the simplified medication adherence questionnaire (SMAQ) in renal transplant patients on tacrolimus. *Nefrología (English Edition)*, 31(6), 690-696.
- 16 Soares, S. M., Diniz, M. Q. D. A., Davino, D. M. B., Albieri, F. B., Santos, A. S., Jesus, E. M., ... & Oliveira-Filho, A. D. (2024). The Simplified Medication Adherence Questionnaire: validation of a Brazilian-Portuguese version in hypertensive adults. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 15, 1348917.
 - 17 Patel, H., Rajput, D. S., & Vaghasiya, J. (2023). Medication Adherence Assessment Scale by Mrs. Hajra Patel and Dr. Jitendra Vaghasiya. *J Young Pharm*, 15(2), 334-337.
 - 18 Yang, J., Li, Q., Feng, Y., & Zeng, Y. (2023). Iron deficiency and iron deficiency anemia: potential risk factors in bone loss. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(8), 6891.
 - 19 Thejpal, R. (2015). Iron deficiency in children: continuing medical education-article. *South African Medical Journal*, 105(7), 14-16.
 - 20 Kulik-Rechberger, B., & Dubel, M. (2024). Iron deficiency, iron deficiency anaemia and anaemia of inflammation-an overview. *Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine*, 31(1). Matsui, Doreen. "Adherence with drug therapy in pregnancy." *Obstetrics and gynecology international* 2012.1 (2012): 796590.
 - 21 Pai, R. D., Chong, Y. S., Clemente-Chua, L. R., Irwinda, R., Huynh, T. N. K., Wibowo, N., ... & Mahdy, Z. A. (2023). Prevention and management of iron deficiency/iron-deficiency anemia in women: an Asian expert consensus. *Nutrients*, 15(14), 3125.
 - 22 Abu-Ouf, N. M., & Jan, M. M. (2015). The impact of maternal iron deficiency and iron deficiency anemia on child's health. *Saudi medical journal*, 36(2), 146.
 - 23 Alemayehu Digssie Gebremariam, A. D. G., Sofonyas Abebaw Tiruneh, S. A. T., Bedilu Abebe Abate, B. A. A., Melaku Tadege Engidaw, M. T. E., & Desalegn Tesfa Asnakew, D. T. A. (2019). Adherence to iron with folic acid supplementation and its associated factors among pregnant women attending antenatal care follow up at Debre Tabor General Hospital, Ethiopia, 2017.